

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION PARADIGM

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Abstract. *The article is discussed that inclusive education has become one of the most important processes in the development of the educational system aimed at providing the opportunity for quality education for all. Regardless of children's physical, mental, intellectual, cultural, ethnic, language and other differences, they included children with special educational needs in quality education center.*

Key words: *Inclusiveness, integration, psychophysiology, consultation, complexes, psycho emotion.*

ПАРАДИГМА ИНКЛЮЗИВНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ

Аннотация. *В статье обсуждается, что инклюзивное образование стало одним из важнейших процессов в развитии образовательной системы, направленной на предоставление возможности получения качественного образования для всех. Независимо от физических, умственных, интеллектуальных, культурных, этнических, языковых и других различий детей, они включали детей с особыми образовательными потребностями в центр качественного образования.*

Ключевые слова: *инклюзивность, интеграция, психофизиология, консультирование, комплексы, психоэмоция.*

In the field of inclusive education, Uzbekistan and the Republic of Karakalpakstan have set their own path of development, taking into the requirements of the world. At the end of the 20th century, in the countries of the world with comprehensive education, such as the USA, Great Britain, Sweden, Germany, and Scandinavia, inclusive education was the main problem of education for underprivileged children. Special conditions, support for the study of children involved in the process of higher education were summarized. In each case, a single model of integration is used, this shows the impossibility of creating a comprehensive model of integration in this field. Inclusive education is a priority in the countries where it is implemented - the focus on the inclusion of the category of children in the education process. Inclusive education program "Education for all" gives all children the opportunity to actively participate in public life in schools, secondary schools, vocational colleges and higher education institutions. This agreement was approved by the United Nations General Assembly and included into the Convention on the Rights

of the Child on December 13, 2006. This Convention was adopted on November 20, 1989, and the Convention "On the Rights of Minorities" was adopted in 2007.

According to the laws of the state policy in the field of education, the equality of the rights of everyone to receive quality education consider the intellectual development of every person, psychological and physiological differences, and the access to education at all levels of the people was defined in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Education".

Inclusive education has become one of the most important processes of the education system aimed at providing access to quality education for all. Regardless of children's physical, mental, intellectual, cultural-ethnic, linguistic and other differences, they included children with special educational needs in the center of quality education, eliminated all hesitations, and for the sake of quality education, namely social education, society.

The modern paradigm of education means preparing children to real life situations as the main task of education. It demands in the world. In fact, such situations are caused by the differences in social norms, which make it difficult to fully implement into the inclusive education process. It is necessary to rely on the activity of the parents in order to find the freedom of separating the children from each other and become a whole community.

Inclusive education is the process of providing equal access to education for all students, taking into account individual capabilities and the need for special education. Children with special educational needs are those who have difficulties in obtaining health-related education, and who require additional educational programs.

According to the famous pedagogue P.Schumann, if the level of mental development of a child is low, the level of education of a teacher should be very high. It is correct idea in the context of inclusive education. The reason is that the teacher retains autonomy when teaching children with special educational needs. [1]

Children will work together with special teachers, psychologists, speech therapists, social teachers, parents and all social partners. This type of intercommunal interaction requires universal flexibility from the teacher. It is necessary for the teacher to think carefully and consider the problems that arise. It demands ability, knowledge, pedagogic master for different education, different categories of children, and level of disease. It is responsible for to know children, to work with children suffering from mental disorders, was very patient with teachers, had a good attitude, was friendly, was very responsible and played an important role in human relations. At present, clearly expressed factors of the development of inclusive education are divided into objective and subjective difficulties. (Figure 1).

Subjective difficulties:

- 1) preparation of standard procedures - monitoring of knowledge for the purpose of restricting the level of education of all children, if necessary, and availability of indicators;
- 2) lack of teaching tools in the Karakalpak language;
- 3) lack of special knowledge of teachers in the development of educational process, lack of stable consultation among all stakeholders;
- 4) absence of special school transport for children with special needs;
- 5) It needs to change, if there are personal problems of the children, it is difficult to get married, there is a relationship between the school and the school, etc.

Objective difficulties:

- 1) low level of material and technical base - lack of spare parts;
- 2) It needs to change, the difficulty of learning the language in the process of teaching children;
- 3) Lack of the cabinets dedicated to the kitchen;
- 4) Lack of course to increase the satisfaction of employees working with children with special needs;
- 5) lack of speech pathologist in Karakalpak language
- 6) lack of special institutions in rural areas employ typhologist, speech therapists, and deaf pedagogues.

In the case of inclusive education, the teacher must perform additional tasks, such as teaching educational content with the help of educational resources, organizing interpersonal relations. The following requirements are established in the Methodological Guidelines for Improving the Education of Children with Special Educational Needs:

- all teachers working in the class with special needs must coordinate the educational programs related to the need for education of each student;
- the whole class project is specially applied to students with special educational needs in the following ways: providing assistance in the improvement of work in the educational process;

to form good relationship in the children society. In the educational system, the process of inclusive education is improved through the forms of pedagogical services. (figure2).

1. Psychological-pedagogical-medical council in Educational collective. This is completed by means of complex dynamics. By order of the director, the board included a speech therapist, a speech therapist, a social teacher, a psychologist, a psychologist, and a class teacher.

2. Consolidation and development works. This is the scope of the psychological-pedagogical complex of activities that have a positive effect on the child's behavior. It is necessary to bring the activity to a normal level, to correct personal shortcomings, to deal with children who need special education, and to manage questionable tasks.

3. Knowledge transfer action. Children are taught to manage the studying process, to develop self-identification activity at every age, and to develop the possibilities and differences of the individual head.

4. Social work. Children's health, family-social, psycho-emotional problems, etc. In the process of socialization, which is connected with the situation, the absence of fluctuations is ensured. It is necessary for the teacher to determine the content, requirements, results of expectations, and assignments according to the evaluation criteria based on the knowledge of the learning behavior of the child with special educational needs, the quality of his daily class participation. It is necessary to use the inclusive strategies taught by the teacher:

- implementation of practical tasks with modeling of schedules;
- the use of step by step directions
- remember the ideas and concepts in the text;
- use role-play games;
- increase interactivity
- work closely with students to distribute instructional tools;
- the use of various methods to achieve specific achievements (points, certificates, awards, etc., and the results of the achievement of joint results);
- to change in teaching methods;
- to motivate their interests and use the informational and technological media contents

- use of computer programs with audio and video recordings;
- tasks should be put in place of time
- giving construction tasks to the ability children;
- more time than usual for all students during mental development;
- providing children with speech disorders with short and simple texts;
- Children with speech disabilities are offered written assignments;
- matching the lexical units used in the students' vocabulary;
- it is necessary to make an effort to improve the motor skills of students with impaired locomotors apparatus by providing children with mild autistic children with appropriate tools;
- asking difficult questions to the students and to control the level of complexity of the questions;
 - to support the activity of children for the full participation of students in the discussion process, to ask constructive questions;
 - use of various methods of completing tasks with prepared answers: drawing diagrams, building models, filming, etc.;
 - encouraging students, supporting their enthusiasm with personal differences;
 - Together with those who focus on problem-solving teaching, "How can I help you in this situation?" "How else can you solve this problem?" lead to metacognitive problems through the use of questions;
 - using reflection to maintain students' self-esteem, improve self-esteem, express themselves, and set goals;
 - digital presentation, electronic exhibition, author's didactic content; use of creative methods such as a sample-original resource;
 - use of learning strategies such as feedback, individual analysis, introspection, group and pair evaluation.

In sum up, in the pedagogical service children with special educational needs, the development of a better sense of oneself from the psychological point of view in the emotional state, at home, at school, in the classroom, in the interaction with others, through the use of technologies that include social-psychological support - the process of inclusive education is became the best pedagogue profession.

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6. REZYUME. Maqolada iknlyuziv ta'limning ahamiyati va imkoniyati cheklangan bolalar bilan olib boriladigan pedagogik-psixologik ishlar haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan.
7. РЕЗЮМЕ. В статье представлена информация о значении инклюзивного образования и педагогико-психологической работе с детьми с ограниченными возможностями здоровья.
8. SUMMARY. The article is devoted to the information on the importance of inclusive education and pedagogical and psychological work with children with disabilities